

Issues Encountered in Learning English Language Skills Using Blended Learning Modality

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Abstract

This study sought to determine three private schools on the Issues Encountered by Grade 10 high school students in Learning English Language Skills using Blended Learning modalities. As a descriptive mixed-method, a pilot-tested self-made online survey questionnaire with a Cronbach Alpha value of .87 (acceptable). In order to validate the survey results, a focus group discussion was conducted with twelve respondents (Grade 10 students) and twelve teachers. Recordings were transcribed and coded. The data gathered were statistically treated using frequency distribution, weighted mean, Pearson r correlation, and Point-Biserial correlation. Data were consolidated, analyzed, and interpreted to come up with conclusions and recommendations. Findings revealed that reading skill was considered most challenging to learn with a weighted mean ($X_w=3.05$) and was frequently encountered issues in learning English language skills using the blended learning modality by grade 10 students. While writing skill was found to be difficult with a weighted mean ($X_w=2.95$). On the other hand, teachers unveiled that speaking skill was considered to be the most difficult to learn, with a weighted mean of ($X_w=3.15$), while reading skill was ascertained to be difficult ($X_w=2.97$). Moreover, there was a significant relationship between students' and teachers' perceptions of the issues in learning the English subject using blended learning and the profile of the respondents. Therefore, teachers should employ new strategies and provide engaging activities suited to students' language needs and learning modes in the new normal education.

Keywords: Learning Modalities, Blended Learning, English Language Skills, Issues, Learning Language Skills

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has caused changes in the teaching-learning process in high school institutions and has influenced teacher-student interaction. As a result of the pandemic, schools were forced to carry out their activities with students using various learning modalities such as online and modular. In this regard, private and government sectors took steps to prevent the virus from spreading and ensure the continuity of teaching-learning process, and schools all over the world adopted distant learning modality as a mode of instruction (Bakhmat, L., et. al. 2021). While internet-based learning is generally regarded as an alternative to traditional learning, it became an essential component for maintaining school activity during the Coronavirus pandemic.

Anent to the DepEd Order No. 13 series of 2020 entitled: Readiness Assessment Checklist for Learning Delivery Modalities in the Learning Continuity Plan of Private Schools. Section 1 is read as follows: In choosing the specific learning delivery modalities to use, the schools shall consider the following: availability of learning resources, the health and well-being of learners and DepEd personnel, national and local directives given, and the choice of parents and learners. Moreover, section 2: Ensure that private schools undertake adequate preparations for the learning delivery modality or modalities chosen. As regards the DepEd Order, CHED adopts and promulgates the following guidelines on Flexible Learning to be implemented by public and private Higher Education Institutions (Deped.gov.ph,2020).

Blended learning as defined by DepEd is a learning delivery that combines face-to-face with any or a mix of online distance learning, modular distance learning, and TV/Radio-based Instruction. Moreover, it integrates online distance learning and in-person delivery of printed materials to the learners' homes through the barangays or villages, especially for those who do not have internet access or interactive facilities in the comforts of the home (Deped.gov.ph,2020).

This new normal setting helps the students become independent so that they can choose the mode of learning that is suited to their level of readiness. Furthermore, it allows them to explore and develop new things that aid critical thinking, which is beneficial for them. Hence, this provides a comprehensive understanding of the new normal way of the teaching-learning process, specifically in learning English language skills.

For this purpose, the researcher sought to determine the issues encountered in learning English Language Skills using the Blended Learning Modality.

Literature Review

Various literatures were reviewed about the study. These are discussed and analyzed relative to the topic on the issues encountered in learning the English language skills using blended learning modality.

BIRTH OF MOST ESSENTIAL LEARNING COMPETENCIES

UNESCO reiterates its position that "education cannot wait." We will lose human capital if learning is halted.

The Department of Education agrees with UNESCO that educational quality, access, and system strengthening cannot be compromised at any time (UNESCO, 2017) and that doing so will harm human capital. Hence, the Department of Education reiterates its commitment to providing quality, accessible, relevant, and liberating Philippine essential education services. Furthermore, this will continue to produce holistic Filipino learners who are equipped with 21st-century skills. Thus, the Bureau of Curriculum Development ensures that learning standards are relevant and adaptable to address the complex, disruptive, volatile, and ambiguous impact of COVID-19 in the Philippines, particularly in the primary education sector.

In connection with the statement above, as cited in Mendoza, J. R. P. (2021), the field implementers and private schools across the country will use the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for SY 2020-2021 temporarily. MELCS will allow the department to tailor instruction to the most important competencies that students must master. In addition, it can also lighten the burden of converting classroom-oriented learning resources into distance learning resources. Furthermore, by providing ample instructional space, the MELCS intends to assist schools in navigating the limited number of school days as they employ multiple delivery schemes.

IMPORTANCE OF THE MOST ESSENTIAL LEARNING COMPETENCIES (MELCS)

To address the impact of COVID-19 in the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) reiterates its commitment to providing quality education relevant to basic education services under the framework of its slogan "Sulong Edukalidad" (Pascua, 2020; Ancheta, R., & Ancheta, H. 2020).

It was also stated that the revised MELCs are part of the DepEd's response to develop a resilient education system, particularly during emergencies, and will be implemented in SY 2020-2021. Moreover, the new MELCs are similar to the original curriculum guide in that it was compressed to focus on the competencies deemed essential and could be implemented using pandemic pedagogy.

In line with this, these can serve as a guide for teachers as they address the instructional needs of students; changes and improvements in teaching methods can help achieve MELC objectives. Hence, teachers are having difficulty delivering the various essential competencies that are prescribed each week (Mendoza, J. R. P., 2021). Although several teachers may struggle to decide which teaching approach to use and apply in each lesson to meet the timeline specified in the MELCs for the topic, on a brighter note, they will be able to determine the best teaching practices to employ in the teaching-learning process to adhere to the MELCS guidelines.

BLENDED LEARNING

Blended learning has become an umbrella term that requires thorough understanding and patience. Blended learning is also used to relate to other blends, such as face-to-face, modular, and online learning, combining different instructional methods, pedagogical approaches, and technologies. However, these blends are not aligned with clear blended learning definitions (Hrastinski 2019). Since blended learning has many meanings, teachers must provide a thorough explanation and a clearer perspective about it, and relate it based on their experiences. It also provides alternatives, more descriptive terms that could be used as a complement or replacement to blended learning. From the standpoint of DepEd, "blended learning" or "hybrid learning" is a fusion of online distance learning and in-person delivery of printed materials to the learners' homes through the barangays for those who do not have internet access and interactive facilities in the comforts of their home. (deped.gov.ph, 2020) Although blended learning has been frequently used, there is still confusion in understanding its meaning and how it affects other learning blends.

TYPES OF BLENDED LEARNING

E-Learning during COVID -19

The emergence of Covid - 19 has had a tremendous effect in Education. However, the teaching-learning process has been struggling because of limited interaction between teachers and students. As a result, challenges have been encountered by teachers and learners. These challenges include difficulties in the accessibility of online learning and in learning English language skills, precisely the four macro skills such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening. In addition, students' engagement with the virtual and digital world is increasing. Today's learners' contacts with

many types of technology for varied objectives have enabled them to be active beneficiaries of e-learning (Vai, Marjorie, & Sosulski, 2015; Mo, 2015). Thus, the need for education updating was required because of the fast advances in technology. Students need to learn at any time and from any place in its way to being achieved (Wolfinger, 2016).

MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AND ITS BENEFITS

Individualized instruction entails allowing learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, depending on the learner's context and other learning resources such as Learner's Materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other study materials. Furthermore, it is the teacher's responsibility to keep track of the students' progress. Through collaboration between students and teachers and with the help of technologies to communicate, students will still learn despite the situation. In connection, any family member or other community stakeholder is encouraged to serve as a para-teacher.

Modular distance learning was developed in response to the need for education among students who prefer traditional learning methods. Once a week, teachers distribute printed modules to students' parents or guardians. The module incorporated various activities, discussions, and performance tasks that the students must complete on their own or with the help of others, like siblings, guardians, or parents.

Here are some of the advantages of modular distance learning (Jim, 2020)

1. Flexible. Students can create their own pace in completing the module's tasks.
2. Student-centered. Each student has their preferred method of learning. Because tasks are completed at their own pace, students develop a sense of responsibility.
3. Accessibility. Local resources are available not always in the form of online resources, but also through community assistance. Hence, they become more inquisitive and creative in searching for answers to their questions before the activities.
4. Simplified. The module's contents are easier to understand than those in the books. As a reference, key points are included as supplements to the books.
5. Cost-efficient. Parents and guardians can save a lot of money on transportation and lodging. The only cost is the printing of modules, which schools bear.

COVID-19 PANDEMIC

On December 31, 2019, WHO received notification of cases of pneumonia of unknown cause in Wuhan City, China, and identified a novel coronavirus as the cause on January 7, 2020, which they named "2019-nCoV" for the time being, and later it was dubbed the "COVID-19 virus." On January 30, 2020, WHO Director-General Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus declared the novel coronavirus outbreak a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC), the organization's highest alert level, due to the 98 cases discovered in 18 countries other than China at the time.

DEPED / CHED ORDER

The current COVID-19 pandemic has created extraordinary challenges and has impacted educational sectors, and no one knows when it will end. Furthermore, every country is currently implementing plans and procedures to contain the virus, but infections are still rising. In the educational context, the new normal should be considered in planning and implementing the "new normal educational policy" to sustain and provide quality education despite lockdown and community quarantine (Tria, J. Z., 2020). In addition, Viner RM, Russell SJ, Croker H, et al. (2020) stated that on March 18, 2020, 107 countries had implemented national school closures in response to the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. Concerning to this crisis, under the relevant provisions of Republic Act (RA) No. 7722, also known as the "Higher Education Act of 1994," Republic Act No. 11469, also known as the "Bayanihan to Heal as One Act," and by commission en Banc (CEB), the Commission adopts and disseminate the following Flexible Learning Guidelines for use by public and private higher education institutions (HEIs).

LEARNING DURING PANDEMIC

The education system has recently been rocked by an unprecedented health crisis that has shaken its foundation. Given the current uncertainty, it is critical to gain a nuanced understanding of students' online learning experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, governments worldwide have launched a crisis response to mitigate the pandemic's impact on education. Curriculum revisions, provision for technological resources and infrastructure, shifts in the academic calendar, and instructional delivery and assessment policies are all part of this response. These developments compelled educational institutions to transition to whole online learning until face-to-face instruction was permitted. The current situation is unique in that it can potentially exacerbate the difficulties encountered during

online learning due to movement restrictions and health protocols (Gonzales et al., 2020; Kapasia et al., 2020; Ancheta, R., & Ancheta, H., 2020).

According to Copeland et al. (2021), the pandemic harmed students' behavioral and emotional functioning, particularly attention and externalizing problems (i.e., mood and wellness behavior) caused by isolation, economic/health effects, and uncertainties. Students expressed concerns about learning and evaluation methods, overwhelming task load, technical difficulties, and confinement in study (Fawaz et al., 2021). To deal with these issues, students took an active role in dealing with the situation, seeking assistance from teachers and relatives, and engaging in recreational activities. These students' active-oriented coping mechanisms were consistent with the findings of Carter et al. (2020), who investigated students' self-regulation strategies.

Related Studies

Various studies were reviewed for their relation to the study. The literature discussed covers the topic explored by the researchers to address the research topic.

In the study of Corcuera, L. C. et al. (2021) entitled "*Learner's Perceptions in Learning English Through Blended Learning Approach*". It concluded that the blended learning approach is one of the novel approaches to incorporating technological advancements into education. However, the difficulties encountered by both instructors and students are common, especially if it is a new addition to the school. While this study aims to use the lenses of 21st-century learners to improve the delivery and implementation of blended learning approaches, specifically in the English language course, it also paved the way for one to deeply discourse one's understanding of combining face-to-face strategies with educational technology, such as examining students' perceptions in the Philippine context.

Interestingly, the study's findings show a positive response in terms of improving their language skills and areas, particularly the English vocabulary, and the development of computer and internet skills, as well as self-paced learning, were identified as two of the blended learning approach's strengths. Moreover, slow internet connections and a preference for printed materials, on the other hand, are perceived limitations of the blended learning approach through the students' lenses. These findings are consistent with the written open-ended questions included in the survey questionnaire. Furthermore, the current study focuses solely on students' perceptions of learning English through the blended learning approach. As a result of the study, it is recommended to investigate English language instructors' perceptions to provide insights that may be able to improve the delivery and implementation of the hybrid teaching and learning process.

Another study from Sriwichai, C. (2020) entitled "*Students' Readiness and Problems in Learning English through Blended Learning Environment*" aims to investigate students' readiness to learn the English language through blended learning and analyze the issues and challenges students face when learning the English language. Data was gathered through a survey questionnaire, and a focus group discussion was administered to understand the students' problems better.

The quantitative data analysis revealed that each item in the questionnaire scored slightly higher than average, indicating that students were well prepared for the implementation of blended learning. However, the FGD responses divulged some issues and challenges that need to be addressed. Some of these are limited access to online lessons, difficulty interacting with teachers and classmates online, a lack of experience and skills in using a Learning Management System, and time management for two learning modes.

In the study of Agung, A. S. N et al. (2020) entitled "*Students' perception of online learning during COVID-19 pandemic: A case study on the English students of STKIP Pamane Talino*" it revealed that the COVID-19 pandemic had caused a significant paradigm shift in Indonesia's education system, shifting from physical to internet-based classrooms. Agung, A. S. N et al. emphasized that the condition necessitates that teachers and students work and study from home appears to be the ideal solution for the sake of people's health; thus, digital classrooms became the lifeline for school. In reality, the transition presents a significant challenge, particularly for those living in underdeveloped areas. According to the current study, most English students are unprepared for this rapid shift in teaching and learning styles.

Several reasons were identified, and they can be divided into three categories:

1. The availability and sustainability of an internet connection
2. The accessibility of teaching media
3. The compatibility of the tools used to access the media

The good news is that the students report that their IT literacy improves while performing the stressful marathon task, though they also report that they and their gadgets are not prepared for this sudden hi-tech change.

Another issue that emerges from the current study, which may be relevant for future research on e-learning during the pandemic COVID-19 in Indonesia, is that it is difficult to find other resources and literature with comparable focus and situation, particularly in rural areas. Furthermore, previous literature frequently deals with online classroom

practice, students' understanding of authentic materials in a CALL environment, software practices, and online assessment aids. However, at STKIP Pamane Talino, we continue to discuss the availability and sustainability of internet connections. In that regard, WhatsApp is a highly recommended medium to use before Google Classroom because users (lecturers and students) are more familiar with it and easier to access. Furthermore, this study demonstrates that online learning requires a user-friendly platform to gain student participation, especially if it is held in rural areas.

Accessibility is a critical factor in online learning success for STKIP Pamane Talino and potentially Indonesia in general. Excellent materials displayed on a magnificent platform will be rendered ineffective if students are unable to access them.

Another study from Karataş, T. Ö., & Tuncer, H. (2020) with the titled "*Sustaining language skills development of pre-service EFL teachers despite the COVID-19 interruption: A case of emergency distance education*". It was resulted that because of the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers and students have abandoned their physical classrooms in favor of emergency distance education (EDE) settings. As a result, maintaining educational quality has become a challenge during this transitional period. Moreover, the objective of Karataş, T. Ö et.al study was to investigate the impact of EDE on the development of language skills (reading, writing, listening, and speaking) in Turkish pre-service teachers of English as a foreign language (EFL).

As a research design, thematic analysis was used, and nine themes emerged for both advantages and disadvantages. The most important theme for both categories is online course content and implementation. Furthermore, the study emphasized the importance of its theme, as it plays a significant role in developing language skills if it is emphasized and appropriately handled. The study concluded that Writing skills were the most beneficial, and speaking skills were the least beneficial in using Emergency Distance Education. Moreover, the participants believed that writing skills were nurtured the most because they were constantly used for almost all homework, assignments, and projects.

Nonetheless, speaking ability was ignored during online courses, and writing replaced speaking as the new mode of communication. The current study's findings encourage EDE preparedness in the event of a second wave. Thus, it is hoped that the study will pave the way for anticipating issues and developing solutions for EDE contexts to maintain sustainability in higher education.

Another study from Hajan, B. H., & Padagas, R. C (2021), entitled "*Blended Learning in A Research Writing Class: Perceptions and Experiences from ESL Secondary Learners*". The development of a highly dynamic and sophisticated educational landscape in modern times has resulted in a highly dynamic and sophisticated educational landscape, and foreign/second language classrooms are no exception to this massive pedagogic change. Moreover, Blended Learning (BL), a newly introduced innovative pedagogy, has received widespread attention in various fields of the second language (L2) teaching and learning, including English for Academic Purposes (EAP). It encourages student-student and student-teacher interactions, lowers communication anxiety, encourages students to become self-directed and independent learners, and improves their academic writing skills in English. However, in the context of Research Writing (RW), BL has received less attention, not to mention that research on BL in an RW classroom in a secondary context, particularly in the Philippines, has been limited. This study assessed and investigated ESL secondary students' perceptions and experiences with Canvas as an online platform in a BL RW class. Furthermore, The Web-based Learning Environment Instrument (WEBLEI), adapted from Chang and Fisher (2003), was administered to 136 Senior High School (SHS) Students from five strands enrolled in Qualitative and Quantitative Research Subjects at a private university in the Philippines using a sequential-explanatory mixed methods research design. Three rounds of focus group discussions were held with 30 participants to gather detailed information about students' experiences in their blended RW class. Canvas was found to be an efficient, practical, convenient, and flexible Learning Management System (LMS) that allowed them to socialize with their peers and teachers. Nonetheless, after sifting through these students' experiences, specific difficulties with an internet connection, system interface, and a lack of proper training for both students and teachers were revealed. The study has pedagogical implications for improving the teaching and learning of research writing in a blended learning modality.

In the study of "*Approaching a reading course via model-based blended learning: EFL learners' insights*", by Radia, B. (2019). It has been asserted that the objectives, content, and organization of this teaching/learning course design contribute to a certain degree in satisfying learners' learning needs within BL, where there is a thoughtful combination of the best components of F2F instruction and online learning. This study, which seeks to determine Algerian students' perceptions and attitudes toward blended learning environments, provides strong evidence certifying that blended learning reading programs positively affect students' reading attitude and motivation and contribute to the improvement of their reading skills. Since this new learning environment has given university students more learning autonomy and freedom, more and more BL courses in which the learning conditions that characterize F2F learning and e-learning are effectively combined to meet the needs of learners are becoming a requirement. Creating the foundation for this innovative learning environment will meet the aspirations and needs of university students of the twenty-first century.

Another study by Syamsuddin, S., and Jimi, A. A. (2019) entitled "*THE USE OF BLENDED LEARNING METHOD IN ENHANCING STUDENTS' LISTENING SKILL FOREVER*". This study aims to determine whether the Blended Learning method improved students' achievement and motivation in learning Listening. In addition, the research subjects were third-semester English Department, Faculty of Letters, University of Sawerigading Makassar students. Furthermore, this study used Classroom Action research, which consisted of two planning, implementation, observation, and reflection cycles. Observation and testing were used to collect data. The data were analyzed in a descriptive comparative fashion. The study's findings revealed that learning to listen through a blended learning method could boost students' achievement. The average score for the initial achievement was 42.07, 61.59 for the first cycle, and 68.11 for the second cycle. Hence, learning to listen through the Blended Learning method increased the students' learning motivation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study is a descriptive mixed-method study that employs quantitative and qualitative research to identify the issues encountered by grade 10 private junior high school students in learning the English language skills using a blended learning modality. It utilized a questionnaire to gather data from the respondents of the selected Private Schools in the Division of Tanjay City. Furthermore, another online survey questionnaire was administered to the teachers of the same school affiliation to back up the answers of the students. In addition, a separate Focus Group Discussion was conducted to validate the data gathered.

Research Environment

The main focus of this study was the three Private schools of Tanjay City Division. An approved letter request is found in Appendix A, page 84.

Casa Marie Learning Institute – It is situated at Brgy. Ilaya, Tanjay City, along the National Road going to Pamplona – Bayawan. It was established last September 25, 1997, and the school was formerly known as Casa Maria Nina Basic Learning Center. The school offers Pre-school, Elementary (Grades 1- 6), Junior High School (Grades 7-10), and Senior High School (Grades 11-12). There was a 35 overall population for grade 10. CMLI used blended learning as their preferred learning modality. Some of the students preferred Modular Distance Learning, wherein parents picked up the printed materials every Monday and returned them every Friday. On the other hand, students in the online learning modality utilize Google Meet as their platform, wherein teachers provide specific links for a specific subject to deliver the lessons to students. (See Appendix H)

Immaculate Heart Academy – Is the only Catholic School in Tanjay City, located beside Roman Catholic Church (Saint James the Greater Parish). Founded last December 8, 1957, by Augustinian Sisters of Our Lady of Consolation. The school offers Kindergarten, Elementary (Grades 1-6), Junior High School (Grades 7-10), and Senior High School (Grade 11-12). IHA utilized the Blended Learning Approach as their mode of learning for the new normal education. For Grade 10, it had a total population of 83. The teacher randomly selected 18 respondents using Modular Distance Learning through learning packets wherein the teacher delivered the learning packets to the meeting area of the parents. Whereas fourteen (14) respondents used Online Distance Learning through Google Meet. (See Appendix H)

Villaflores College – It is situated at Legaspi St. Brgy. 8, Tanjay City Negros Oriental beside Public Cemetery. Founded last February 25, 1952, it was formerly known as Tanjay Institute or TI. The school offers Kindergarten, Elementary (Grades 1- 6), Junior High School (Grades 7-10), Senior High School (Grades 11-12), College (BEED, BSED, BSBA), and Master's Program (MAED – Educational Management, Guidance and Counseling). It also offered a Blended Learning Approach as the new normal in education. VC had an overall population of 85 enrollees in grade 10 but selected only twelve (12) learners using Digital Modules Learning modality through Edmodo, while twenty (20) respondents used Online Distance Modality through Zoom. Hence, VC used digital modules instead of printed materials in delivering the lesson. (See Appendix H)

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study encompassed 94 grade 10 Junior High School students of selected Private Schools in the Tanjay City Division. The following distributions of each school were as follows.

School	Number of Respondents
Casa Marie Learning Institute	30
Immaculate Heart Academy	32
Villaflores College	32
Total	94

In addition, Casa Marie Learning Institute has only 1 section for Grade 10. Immaculate Heart Academy and Villaflores College have three sections, making it the largest number of respondents. Moreover, among the 94 respondents, only 12 students participated in the Focus Group Discussion through Google Meet, facilitated by an English Language teacher with the guide questions. (See Appendix E)

Research Instrument

The study employed the following research instruments to gather data.

Students' Questionnaire: This study utilized a teacher-made survey questionnaire as the primary tool in gathering the data. The researcher presented the questionnaire to panelists for refinement. A reliability test was conducted and yielded an acceptable Cronbach Alpha value of .87 (acceptable) before it was administered. Moreover, the questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part I includes the profile of the respondents (sex, school affiliation, availability of devices/gadgets at home, and accessibility to the internet). Part II was the issues encountered in learning the English language skills using a blended learning modality. (See Appendix B) Part II also utilized Likerts' 4-point scale with a corresponding verbal description.

Scale	Interval	Verbal Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree

Focus Group Discussion: This was conducted to validate the responses of the respondents in the survey. It was composed of four student respondents and teachers in each school; a total of 12 student respondents and teachers participated. (See Appendix E)

Teachers' Questionnaire: The same survey questionnaire was given to the teachers using Google Forms. The objective of the inclusion of the teachers' answers, including FGD, was to validate the students' answers.

Research Procedures

The following procedures were employed to gather the needed data:

The researcher formulated a questionnaire used in the study, which was refined based on the assessment and feedback given by the experts.

The researcher determined the schools to be included in the survey through random and cluster sampling. Once approved, the researcher seeks permission from the school's principals to distribute the survey questionnaires to the respondents. Moreover, the researcher also sent a parent's consent form to the parents of the respondents. To reach the respondents and the teachers, the researcher created an online questionnaire through Google Forms to ensure proper health protocols. Each student and the teachers were given the link to access the survey questionnaire. Focus Group discussions were conducted by language teachers with guide questions. No name was mentioned in any part of the study for the assessment to observe confidentiality.

English language teachers in the private schools create their learning packets or modules following the MELCs provided by DepEd. The lessons indicated in their modular learning were in congruence with the lessons in online learning. However, the activities posed by the teachers were modified since two of the macro skills (speaking & listening) are rarely used in modular learning, wherein students were tasked to record themselves while memorizing a poem or giving a speech. In listening, students were given links for a particular video to view and listen to some speeches. In this regard, students were still able to learn the competencies in the MELCs, achieve the target language, and hone their English language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing).

Data was consolidated, statistically treated, analyzed, and interpreted to develop findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Statistical Treatment

These responses are statistically treated to describe the respondents' responses to various items in the survey questionnaire as accurately as possible. This study used Microsoft Excel for frequency counting, percentage computation, ranking system, weighted mean, and composite mean. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v 16.0) was used for Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and t-Test.

Frequency. This is used to determine how many respondents belong to the same group when classified according to their profile.

Weighted Mean. This is utilized to determine the score of the issues encountered by private school students in answering the English subject using a blended learning modality.

Mean. This is to get the average scores when the respondents were arranged according to a particular group.

Pearson r Correlation – This is used to determine the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the degree of the perceived issues.

Point-Biserial Correlation- utilized to find the relationship between the non-parametric variables (e.g., sex, school, etc.) and the perceptions on issues encountered by private school students in answering the English subject using blended learning modality.

Results

The results of the statistical analysis are presented, and the interpretation of the findings is evident in this section. These are presented in tables following the sequence of the specific research problem in the study. It specifically concerns the following: 1) profile of the students in terms of sex, school affiliation, availability of devices/gadgets at home, accessibility to the internet; 2) issues encountered by Grade 10 private school junior high students in learning English language skills using blended learning modality. (Reading, Listening, Speaking, and Writing); 3) the perceptions of the teachers in terms of the issues encountered in learning English language skills using blended learning modality in terms of Reading, Listening, Speaking, and Writing; 4) Significant relationship between the profile of the students on the perceived issues in learning the English language skills using blended learning modality; and 5) significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers on the issues encountered in learning the English language skills using blended learning modality.

1. PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

This section presents the analysis of the tabulated data on the profile of the Grade 10 Private Junior High School students. The profile of the respondents in terms of sex, school affiliation, availability of devices and gadgets at home, and accessibility to the internet was included with the notion that these could influence their issues encountered in learning the English language skills using blended learning modality, which will affect their performance task.

Table 1.1 Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	41.49
Female	55	58.51
Total	94	100.00

Table 1.2 reveals that majority of the respondents were females with a frequency of 55 or 58.51%, while males had 39 or 41.49% of the total population. Notably, cited in (Jackson et al., 2001) that females are more likely to engage in an online activity involving conversation and information exchange, while males prefer to involve in information seeking. On the contrary, a study conducted by Harb, J. et al. (2014) entitled "Gender differences in attitudes towards learning oral skills using technology" states that females and males respond equally towards learning speaking and listening skills. Hence, students' gender should also be given consideration in learning English language skills. Therefore, teachers must address the needs of every learner of any gender to enhance and develop their English Language Skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing).

Table 1.2 Respondents' School Affiliation

School	Frequency	Percentage
Immaculate Heart Academy	32	34.04
Villaflores College	32	34.04
Casa Marie Learning Institute	30	31.91
Total	94	100.00

The table showed that Immaculate Heart Academy and Villaflores College had an equal frequency of 32, with a percentage of 34.04 of the total population, while Casa Marie Learning Institute had a frequency of 30 and a percentage of 31.91 of the total population. This indicates that 100% of each school's respondents participated and answered the survey questionnaire. In addition, Immaculate Heart Academy and Villaflores College were both categorized as big schools, while Casa Marie Learning School, on the other hand, was categorized as a small school, reason why there were more participants in IHA and VC compared to CMLI.

According to Willms, J. D. (2003), youths' daily lives revolve around school. They consider education to be critical to their long-term success, well-being, and this mindset is reflected in their participation in academic and non-academic endeavors. Willms added that humans affiliate with a wide range of things, including ideas and possibly the institutions interact. Moreover, school affiliation plays a vital role in molding students' well-being and individuality. It provides students' sense of belongingness and acceptance. Through which they build confidence and trust, as well as participate in all their learning undertakings. Thus, school became their second home.

Table 1.3 Available devices/gadgets at home

Gadgets	Frequency	Percentage
Mobile Phones	80	57.14%
Tablet	11	7.86%
Laptop	42	30%
Desktop Computer	7	5%
Total Gadgets available at home	140	100%

Table 1.3 showed that most respondents were using smartphones with 57.14% or a frequency of 80 compared to laptop with 30% or a frequency of 42, tablet with 7.86% or a frequency of 11 and desktop computer with a frequency of 7 or 5%. Cited from Castillo et al. (2013), Khubiyari et al. (2016) mobile learning technologies allow users to access online educational resources using mobile devices such as smartphones, notebooks, tablets, and the like anywhere and anytime. Moreover, Tayebinik, M. et al. (2012) implies that apart from computer-based technologies, mobile learning has been recognized as a valuable tool in distance education. Tayebinik, M. et al. added that, Mobile phones are a more widespread technology (MMS) because majority of the people own mobile phones that are equipped with the following services: Bluetooth, Wireless Internet (Wi-Fi), General Packet Radio System (GPRS), Global Systems for Mobile (GSM), and multimedia messaging. Mobile learners are then given direct access to the information they need on their phones. These characteristics prompted educators to incorporate this system into the distance education program. Furthermore, the development of mobile devices has altered the face of English language teaching and learning by focusing on portable devices known as "mobile learning" or M-learning systems which are regarded as distinct teaching and learning approaches (Tayebinik, M. et al. 2012, Dawabi et al., 2003).

Table 1.4 Accessibility to the internet

Gadgets	Frequency	Percentage
Broadband Internet	29	30.851
Mobile data	61	64.894
Public Wi-Fi (Malls, Barangays)	3	3.191
Private Wifi (Fast-food, Coffee shops)	1	1.064
Total	94	100%

Table 1.4 revealed that majority of the respondents had an accessible internet connection using mobile data with a frequency of 61 or 64.894% in comparison to Broadband internet, with the frequency of 29 or 30.851%, public Places WiFi with frequency of 3 or 3.191 and Private Wifi with a frequency of 1 or 1.064%. This shows that students would perform the task assigned, especially if the internet is needed, since they have access to the internet. According to Nalliveettil, G. M. et al. (2016), mobile phones with internet access can search thousands of websites and present the reader with very accurate information. Mobile devices with WiFi capabilities and Wireless Application Protocol (WAP) that distribute information and learning materials via the internet are called technological mobility. Hence, most students nowadays use smartphones, and it is evident that accessing the internet involves using their mobile data. In short, students can access the internet anytime they go to places with cellphone signals using their mobile data.

2. Issues encountered by Grade 10 private school junior high students in learning English language skills using blended learning modality. (Reading, Listening, Speaking, and Writing)

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Verbal Description
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree

Table 2.1 Listening Skills

Listening Difficulty in...	Students		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
A. Listening to teachers and classmate’s online discussion	0.68	3.01	3.5	Agree
B. Listening to audio materials used in online class	0.73	3.01	3.5	Agree
C. Listening to different accents used in audio materials	0.77	3.05	2 nd	Agree
D. Listening to speeches (ex. Public Speaking)	0.79	3.06	1 st	Agree
E. Comprehending questions asked	0.73	2.90	5 th	Agree
Composite Mean	0.74	3.00		Agree

Table 2.1 appears that “*Difficulty in listening to speeches*” had the highest rank with the weighted mean of 3.06, followed by “*Difficulty in listening to different accents used in audio materials*” with the weighted mean of 3.05; next was comprehending questions with a weighted mean of 2.90. On the other hand, “*Difficulty in listening to teachers’ and classmates’ online discussions*” and “*Difficulty in listening to audio materials used in online classes*” had a weighted mean of 3.01. All had a verbal description of AGREE, which means that respondents considered these indicators as factors having difficulty in learning the listening skills using blended modality. This result was validated by the students through FGD. According to P7, as “*The lessons were difficult to understand in some instances, because of online classes.*” (P7:L58-61) This statement was also agreed by P4, who pointed out that “*Listening is the most difficult skills to learn using blended learning modality.*” (P4:L183-188) P9 added that “*Based on experience, the most difficult among the four macro skills using blended learning modality was listening skills.*” (P9:190-193) As a result, student participants 7, 4, and 9 had the same experience on the issues encountered. It can be concluded that these participants were not yet adjusted and adapted to the new normal learning modality.

Furthermore, Aji, Mahendra (2017) pointed out that teachers used blended learning to keep the students interested and easily understand while listening. Thus, listening skills will be learned if teachers and students collaborate for mutual benefit. It is suggested that differentiated instructions or alternative tactics suitable to the type of learning modality employed must be used by the teachers, and students must diligently develop their listening skills despite the highlighted issues and challenges faced.

2.2 Speaking Skills

Speaking Skills Difficulty in...	Students		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
F. Delivering an impromptu speech on a particular issue	0.80	3.20	1 st	Agree
G. Giving ideas or inputs in a class through online discussion	0.79	2.88	4 th	Agree
H. In presenting a topic using correct grammar and well-pronounced words	0.75	3.01	2 nd	Agree
I. Asking questions regarding the instructions found in the modules (ex., phone call)	0.84	2.80	5 th	Agree
J. Answering questions using the English language	0.84	2.97	3 rd	Agree
Composite Mean	0.80	2.97		Agree

Table 2.2 presents five difficulties in learning speaking skills using a blended learning modality. “*Difficulty in delivering an impromptu speech on a particular issue*” ranked first with a weighted mean of 3.20. “*Difficulty in presenting a topic using correct grammar and well-pronounced words*” (3.01) was second in rank. “*Difficulty in answering questions using the English language*” (2.97) ranked third. “*Difficulty in giving ideas or inputs in a class through online discussion*” (2.88) ranked fourth, and “*Difficulty in asking questions regarding the instructions found in the*

modules" (ex., phone call) (2.80) ranked fifth. It was evident that all indicators were interpreted as "Agree". It suggests that students believed and agreed that these indicators were experienced in learning their speaking skills using a blended learning modality.

Based on the assessment of the FGD conducted, students discovered that speaking skills are challenging to develop using a blended learning modality. P4 states that "Can no longer practice speaking skills activities such as oral recitation, tongue twister, and poems." (P4:L29-32) It was also affirmed by P1 that " Won't be able to practice proper pronunciation of difficult words" (P1:L233-237) P11 pointed out that there was "limited interaction with our teachers and classmates" (P11:L209-213) P12 added that "Speaking and reading skills are not practiced. Limited time to answer because of too many activities." (P12:L105-116) P2 also added that " We can't practice our speaking skills." (P2:L220-223). Subsequently, participants mentioned above had encountered the same difficulties. It can be inferred that these participants struggled to adapt to the new standard teaching-learning process.

However, Isda, I. D., et al. (2021) cited a positive effect of using a blended learning modality in learning speaking skills. Thus, learning speaking skills using a blended learning modality has become a challenge since students were still adjusting and adapting to the sudden shift of learning modality in this new normal setting of teaching-learning. Therefore, teachers must facilitate fun and dynamic communicative activities to stimulate students' learning interest and motivation. Students must actively participate in all the activities provided to develop and enhance their speaking skills. In addition, teachers and students should build great teamwork to attain the goals and objectives set for learning.

Table 2.3 Reading Skills

Reading Skills Difficulty in...	Students		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
a. familiarizing research terminologies (Investigative research, Phenomenological research)	0.79	3.35	1 st	Strongly Agree
b. interpreting reading material such as modules, online output through google forms	0.81	2.89	4 th	Agree
c. analyzing illustrations, graphs, and graphic organizers	0.80	3.04	2 nd	Agree
d. identifying the main idea of a paragraph	0.81	2.97	5 th	Agree
e. analyzing text structure (ex. Figures of Speech, Poems)	0.75	3.01	3 rd	Agree
Composite Mean	0.79	3.05		Agree

Table 2.3 presents the issues encountered by students in learning the English language skills using a blended learning modality. The results showed that 1 out of 5 issues was highly regarded as "Strongly Agree"; this was "Difficulty in familiarizing research terminologies (Investigative research, Phenomenological research" (3.35) ranked first. On the other hand, four issues were interpreted as "Agree" to wit: "Difficulty in analyzing illustrations, graphs, and graphic organizers" (3.04) ranked second, "Difficulty in analyzing text structure" (ex. Figures of Speech, Poems) (3.01) ranked third, "Difficulty in interpreting reading material such as modules, online output through google forms" (2.89) ranked fourth, and "Difficulty in identifying the main idea of a paragraph" (2.97) ranked fifth.

Reading skills play a vital role in the process of students' learning. Hence, honing students' reading skills must take into account. From the findings of the FGD, students find it challenging to learn reading skills during blended learning. P12 cited that "Speaking and reading skills are not practiced." (P12:L110-111) It was also attested by P2 that there was "Difficulty in understanding words used in the research subject." (P2:L22-23) P9 affirmed "Lack of understanding on the terms in research." (P9:L71-76) P10 added that "Our lessons are also challenging to understand, especially the terms in research. I don't know the procedure on how to make and write a research paper." (P10:L83-86) Notwithstanding, Radia, B. (2019) recommended that teachers use excellent instructional methods suitable to students' needs and the modality used for learning to improve and boost students' reading abilities. Hence, students must adopt independent learning, and teachers must utilize flexible learning to address the issues encountered. They must work together collaboratively to achieve the target goal of learning and improving reading skills.

Table 2.4 Writing Skills

Writing Skills Difficulty in...	Students		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
a. Writing a sentence following correct grammar rules	0.82	2.89	4 th	Agree
b. Writing a poem using figurative language	0.79	2.94	2 nd	Agree

c. Writing a research paper	0.85	3.18	1 st	Agree
d. Identifying grammar rules	0.84	2.91	3 rd	Agree
e. Writing an opinion or essay using conjunctions (ex. because, therefore)	0.90	2.81	5 th	Agree
Composite Mean	0.84	2.95		Agree

Table 2.4 presents five issues Private Grade 10 Junior High Students encountered in learning English language skills using a blended learning modality. These issues and their corresponding weighted mean are as follows: "Difficulty in writing a research paper" (3.18) ranked first, followed by "Difficulty in writing a poem using figurative language" (2.94) ranked second, next was "Difficulty in identifying grammar rules" (2.89) ranked third, then "Difficulty in writing a sentence following correct grammar rules" (2.89) ranked fourth, and "Difficulty in writing an opinion or essay using conjunctions (ex. because, therefore)" (2.81) ranked fifth. It was apparent that all five issues were regarded as "Agree."

Based on the FGD, students find it challenging to acquire writing skills using a blended learning modality. P6 pointed out "Difficulty of the lesson especially in writing research." (P6:L53-54). Affirmed by P8 that "Difficulty in understanding the new words in our lesson and I don't know how to use it in writing a sentence." (P8:L63-69) P10 added that "I don't know the procedure on how to make and write a research paper." (P10:L85-86)

However, Hajan, B. H., et al. (2021) states that there is a positive outcome in learning writing skills using a blended learning modality. First, students had developed and enhanced their academic writing skills through engaging the online platforms. Second, it also motivates students to be flexible and learn independently. But, due to the sudden shift of learning modality or the delivery of learning, students and teachers experienced different learning difficulties using blended learning modality. They are still adjusting and adapting to the new normal ways in the teaching-learning process. Hence, students and teachers played a significant role in the teaching- learning process. They must have the connection and work as a team to achieve the common goal of learning writing skills in the new normal.

3. Perceptions of teachers in terms of the issues encountered in learning the English Language skills using blended learning modality.

Table 3.1 Listening Skills

Listening Skills Difficulty in...	Teachers		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
a. Listening to teachers and classmate's online discussion	0.67	3.08	1 st	Agree
b. Listening to audio materials used in online class	0.60	3.00	3	Agree
c. Listening to different accents used in audio materials	0.72	2.83	5 th	Agree
d. Listening to speeches (ex. Public Speaking)	0.60	3.00	3	Agree
e. Comprehending questions asked	0.74	3.00	3	Agree
Composite Mean	0.67	2.98		Agree

The perceptions of the teachers in terms of the issues students encountered in learning the listening skills using the blended learning modality are reflected on table 3.1. It appeared that all indicators had weighted means with verbal descriptions "Agree." Specifically, these indicators and their corresponding weighted means were as follows: "Difficulty in listening to teachers' and classmates' online discussions" (3.08), "Difficulty in listening to audio materials used in an online class" (3.00), "Difficulty in listening to different accents used in audio materials" (2.83), "Difficulty in listening to speeches (ex. Public Speaking)" (3.00), and "Difficulty in comprehending questions asked (3.00). The composite mean score obtained for the teachers' perceptions of the issues students encountered in learning the listening skills using the blended learning modality was (2.98 and had a verbal description of "agree." It means that based on teachers' observations, it was evident that students had experienced these challenges using the blended learning modality.

Based on the FGD conducted, English language teachers confirmed that students encountered these issues in learning the listening skills using a blended learning modality. Moreover, it was a prerequisite in implementing the new normal way of teaching-learning since teachers are facilitators of learning. It was reflected in the following lines:

"Based on my experience as a teacher during this pandemic, one of the issues I encountered in my online class was that other students were not listening to the class discussion. (P4:L58-68). P8 added that "I cannot assess students' listening skills." (P8:L115-128).

Cited from Kop and Hill (2008), the fundamental purpose of learning is connecting and providing information into a learning community that will enhance and develop learners' skills. Therefore, teachers must provide varied strategies suited to the learners' needs to address the issues encountered and meet the requirements for learning.

Table 3.2 Speaking Skills

Speaking Skills Difficulty in...	Teachers		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
a. Delivering an impromptu speech on a particular issue	0.65	3.33	1.5	Strongly Agree
b. Giving ideas or inputs in a class through online discussion	0.85	3.00	4.5	Agree
c. In presenting a topic using correct grammar and well - pronounced words	0.78	3.33	1.5	Strongly Agree
d. Asking questions regarding the instructions found in the modules (ex. phone call)	0.79	3.08	3 rd	Agree
e. Answering questions using the English language	0.74	3.00	4.5	Agree
Composite Mean	0.76	3.15		Agree

The table above shows teachers' perceptions of the five issues students encountered in learning speaking skills using a blended learning modality. It was revealed that 2 (two) out of 5 (five) difficulties had a verbal description of "strongly agree," which means that teachers strongly believed that these issues were evident and were experienced by the students in the new normal way of teaching. "Difficulty in delivering an impromptu speech on a particular issue" and "Difficulty in presenting a topic using correct grammar and well-pronounced words" had a weighted mean of (3.33). Meanwhile, the remaining three indicators had obtained a verbal description of "agree," precisely these issues were as follows: "Difficulty in asking questions regarding the instructions found in the modules (ex. phone call)" (3.08), "Difficulty in giving ideas or inputs in a class through online discussion" (3.00), and "Difficulty in answering questions using the English language" (3.00). The composite mean score obtained on teachers' perception was 3.15 and had a verbal description of "agree". This means that students are still adapting and familiarizing the new modality of learning.

From the findings of the FGD, teachers pointed out that the students encountered these issues in learning the speaking skills using a blended learning modality. P4 states that "Based on my experience as a teacher during this pandemic, one of the issues I had encountered in my online class is that some students cannot pronounce the words correctly." (P4:L58-68) Moreover, P1 added that "It's really difficult if the student is taking the modular type of learning because they cannot use their speaking skills." (P1:L310-319) In addition, P12 cited that "With my point of view, speaking is the most difficult skill to teach." Furthermore, Karataş, T. Ö. et al. (2020) state that due to the threat posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, students and teachers have disregarded traditional classroom settings to pave the way for blended learning. During online classes, speaking skills were overlooked, and writing skill took the place of speaking skill as the new form of communication. Hence, students and teachers must prepare themselves for the new normal way of the teaching-learning process. Teachers as facilitators of learning should ensure that speaking skills are also given importance despite this situation.

Table 3.3 Reading Skills

Reading Skills Difficulty in...	Teachers		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
a. Familiarizing research terminologies (Investigative research, Phenomenological research)	0.51	3.08	1 st	Agree
b. interpreting reading material such as modules, online output through google forms	0.58	2.83	5 th	Agree
c. Analyzing illustrations, graphs, and graphic organizers	0.74	3.00	2.5	Agree
d. Identifying the main idea of a paragraph	0.60	3.00	2.5	Agree
e. Analyzing text structure (ex. Figures of Speech, Poems)	0.67	2.92	4 th	Agree
Composite Mean	0.62	2.97		Agree

Table 3.3 presents five difficulties students encountered in learning reading skills using a blended learning modality. It was evident that all of the indicators were regarded as "agree." These difficulties and their corresponding weighted

means were "Difficulty in familiarizing research terminologies (Investigative research, Phenomenological research)" (3.08), "Difficulty in analyzing illustrations, graphs, and graphic organizers" (3.00), "Difficulty in identifying the main idea of a paragraph" (3.00), "Difficulty in analyzing text structure (ex. Figures of Speech, Poems)" (2.92) and "Difficulty in interpreting reading material such as modules, online output through google forms" (2.83). The composite mean score derived for the teachers' perceptions was 2.97 and had a verbal description as agree.

Based on the FGD conducted, P6 states that "Students' level of understanding is diminishing, like my grade 10 class, we have a lesson about how to make a research paper. My students kept on asking me *"lisod kaayo ang research ma'am, dili mi kasabot kaayo sa mga terminologies nga gigamit."* (P6:L95-98). In addition, P3 affirms that "Based on my experience, ma'am, the most difficult macro skill to teach nowadays, most specifically in these times of pandemic, is the reading skill." (P3:L252-254). Moreover, according to Carter et al. (2020), to ensure that students' concerns and issues will be addressed, they must actively be involved or engaged in recreational activities that strengthen their young minds and boost their interest in learning.

Thus, teachers must determine the issues encountered by the students for them to be able to identify their specific needs and provide interventions to improve students' reading skills.

Table 3.4 Writing Skills

Writing Skills Difficulty in...	Teachers		Rank	Verbal Description
	STD	Wx		
f. Writing a sentence following correct grammar rules	0.43	3.00	4.5	Agree
g. Writing a poem using figurative language	0.60	3.00	4.5	Agree
h. Writing a research paper	0.65	3.33	1 st	Strongly Agree
i. Identifying grammar rules	0.72	3.17	2 nd	Agree
j. Writing an opinion or essay using conjunctions (ex. because, therefore)	0.67	3.08	3 rd	Agree
Composite Mean	0.61	3.12		Agree

Table 3.4 shows the Teachers' perception of the issues encountered in learning the writing skills using the blended learning modality. It was apparent that one of these indicators was regarded as "strongly agree." This issue encountered, and their corresponding weighted mean were as follows: "Difficulty in writing a research paper" (3.33), However, four indicators were interpreted as "agree", these were "Difficulty in identifying grammar rules" (3.17), "Difficulty in Writing an opinion or essay using conjunctions (ex. because, therefore)" (3.08), "Difficulty in writing a sentence following correct grammar rules" (3.00), and "Difficulty in writing a poem using figurative language" (3.00). The composite mean score derived for the teachers' perception of the issues encountered in learning the writing skills using the blended learning modality was 3.12, with a verbal description of "agree". Moreover, teachers validated the said issues during the focus group discussion. P9 pointed out that "For me, it is the writing skill, nowadays, we cannot guarantee that students are the ones who are writing their answers both in modular and online learning." (P9:L342-353)

Furthermore, Hajan, B. H., et al. (2021) cited those modern times have established a practical and sophisticated educational landscape. Teachers ensured that students actively participated in the online survey to determine the issues encountered and address these issues by providing the necessary interventions. Hence, teachers and students must have constant connections or communication to track students' progress and build a harmonious relationship to boost students' interest in learning.

4. Test of significant relationship between the profile of students on the perceived issues in learning English language skills using blended learning modality.

Variables		r value using Point Biserial and Pearson r tests	p value	Remarks	Decision
Perceived issues in learning English language skills using blended learning modality	School Affiliation	.22	.03	Significant	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Sex	-.18	.08	Not Significant	Failed to Reject Null
	Gadgets used	.30	.004	Significant	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Internet Connectivity	.11	.30	Not Significant	Failed to Reject Null

Significant Level	.05 alpha
N	94

Table 4 presents the results of the test of the significant relationship between the profile of students on the perceived issues in learning English language skills using blended learning modality. **School affiliation** $r(94) = .22, p = .034$, and **Gadgets used during blended learning modality** $r(94) = .30, p = .004$ were significant to 0.05 alpha. While **Sex** $r(94) = -.18, p = .08$ and **Internet Connectivity** $r(94) = .11, p = .30$ were not significant to 0.05 alpha. This implies that the school affiliation of students and the gadgets being used during blended learning activity have positive or negative effects in learning English language skills.

5. Test of significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers on the issues encountered in learning English language skills using blended learning modality.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	2.995212766	2.70355958
Variance	0.397423073	0.427162069
Observations	94	12
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	14	
t Stat	1.46	
P(T<=t) one-tail	.08	
t Critical one-tail	1.76	
P(T<=t) two-tail	.17	
t Critical two-tail	2.14	

Table 5 shows the test of significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students on the issues encountered in learning English language

skills using blended learning modality. The **t stat value is equal to 1.46 and is less than the t-critical two-tail of 2.14, while the computed p-value is equal to .17** (two-tail) and is not significant at .05 alpha. This means that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students on the issues encountered in learning English language skills using blended learning. They have common perceptions on the difficulties experienced by students in the learning process.

Discussion

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The following were the findings from the study which are revealed in the order which they appeared on the problem statement:

The result of the study presented the following findings:

Profile of the students

Based on the data gathered, both VC and IHA had 32 respondents compared to CMLI, which had 30 respondents only. The majority of the respondents were females, with a frequency of 55 or 58.51%, while males had 39 or 41.49% of the total population. In addition, most of the respondents had mobile phones with a frequency of 80 (57.14%), followed by laptops with 42 (30%), then tablets with a frequency of 11 (7.86%), and lastly, desktop computers with a frequency of 7 (5%). On the accessibility to the internet, it appeared that majority of the respondents were using mobile data, which had a frequency of 61 (64.894%), next was broadband internet with a frequency of 29 (30.851%) followed by public Wifi (Malls, Barangays) with a frequency of 3 (3.191%) and private wifi with a frequency of 1 or (1.064%). Based on the issues encountered by students in learning the English language skills, it was found that:

In terms of the listening skills, "Difficulty in listening to different speeches (ex., Public speaking)" had the highest weighted mean of 3.06, while "Difficulty in comprehending questions asked" had the lowest weighted mean of 2.90. Both weighted means had a verbal description of "Agree." With these points, the composite mean was 2.84, which was interpreted as Agree, which means that the respondents believed that the issues encountered in learning their listening skills are essential to enhance students' listening skills for effective communication in the new normal setting.

Regarding the issues encountered in learning students' speaking skills, "Delivering an impromptu speech on a particular issue" was apparently to be the top among others with a weighted mean of 3.20 and a verbal description of "Strongly Agree." while "Difficulty in asking questions regarding the instructions found in the modules (ex. phone call)" had the lowest weighted mean of 2.80 and appeared "Agree." Thus, speaking skills play an essential role, especially in students' communicative competence in dealing with others to communicate effectively in order to express their ideas and thoughts using the different learning modes in the new normal way. Concerning the issues encountered in learning reading skills using the Blended Learning modality "Difficulty in familiarizing research terminologies (Investigative research, Phenomenological research)" revealed as the top among others with a weighted mean of 3.35, which had a verbal description of Strongly Agree. Apparently, "Difficulty in identifying the main idea of a paragraph" had a weighted mean of 2.97 and a verbal description of Agree. It was evident that students struggled more in learning research. It is believed that reading skills are significantly impact by providing new strategies for learning reading skills suited to the new normal setting. Correspondingly, regarding the issues encountered in learning the writing skills using the blended learning modality the result was that "Difficulty in writing a research paper" had the highest composite mean of 3.18, while "Difficulty in writing an opinion or essay using conjunctions (ex. because, therefore)" had the lowest weighted mean of 2.81, both weighted means had a verbal description of "Agree." Along with the composite mean of 2.95 with a verbal description of Agree, this can be concluded that students find the need to master writing skills, specifically in writing a research paper and identifying grammar rules. Respondents recognized the importance of writing skills because they believed it would help them think critically, broaden vocabulary, communicate well, develop ideas, and improve grammar.

Based on the teachers' perceptions of the issues encountered by the students in learning the English language skills using blended learning modality, it was found out that:

Regarding students' listening skills, "Difficulty in listening to teachers and classmates' online discussion" had the highest weighted mean of 3.08, while "Difficulty in listening to different accents used in audio materials" had the lowest weighted mean of 2.83. Both weighted means had a verbal description of Agree. It can be concluded that teachers concurred that students struggled in learning their listening skills using a blended learning modality. It was confirmed that listening to online class discussions influences students' learning and comprehension. Anent to students' speaking skills, "Difficulty in delivering an impromptu speech on a particular issue" and "Difficulty in presenting a topic using correct grammar and well-pronounced words" had a tie score on the highest weighted mean of 3.33, with verbal descriptions of "Strongly Agree." While "Difficulty in giving ideas or inputs in a class through online discussion" and "Difficulty in answering questions using the English language" also had a tie on the lowest weighted mean of 3.00 and a verbal description of "Agree." Therefore, teachers believed that speaking skills play an essential part in the English language as it is the most fundamental skill that students need to acquire. Thus, teachers had also observed the same issues encountered by the students on speaking skills which influences their academic progress.

Concerning students' reading skills, "Difficulty in familiarizing research terminologies (Investigative research, Phenomenological research)" had the highest weighted mean of 3.08 while "Difficulty in interpreting reading materials such as modules, online output through google forms" had the lowest weighted mean of 2.83. Both weighted means had a verbal description of "Agree," which means that teachers affirmed the issues encountered in learning students' reading skills using blended learning modality were experienced by students. Teachers also concluded that reading skills play an essential role in enhancing the comprehension and analytical abilities of the students in the new normal way of the teaching-learning process.

Regarding students' writing skills, "Difficulty in writing a research paper" had the highest weighted mean of 3.33, with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree." While "Difficulty in writing a sentence following correct grammar rules"

and "Difficulty in writing a poem using figurative language" both had weighted means of 3.00 with a verbal description of "Agree," this means that teachers confirmed that students encountered these issues. Thus, teachers believed in the importance of writing skills in students' learning, in improving their communication skills and sharpening their creativity and imagination.

Significant relationship between the profile of students on the perceived issues in learning English language skills using blended learning modality.

The statements below summarize the findings on the significant relationship between the profile of the students on the perceived issues in learning English language skills using a blended learning modality. The School affiliation $r(94) = .22, p = .03$ and Gadgets used for learning $r(94) = .30, p = .004$ were significant to 0.05 alpha. While Sex $r(94) = -.18, p = .09$ and Internet Connectivity $r(94) .11, p = .30$ were not significant to .05 alpha. This means that the school affiliation of students and the gadgets being used during blended learning activity had a positive or negative impact on their ability to learn English language skills.

Significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers on the issues encountered in learning English language skills using blended learning modality.

The statements below summarize the findings on the significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students on the issues encountered in learning English language skills using blended learning modality. The computed t-stat value was equal to 1.46 and was less than the t-critical two-tail of 2.14, while the computed p-value was equal to .17 (two-tail) and was not significant to .05 alpha. This means that there was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and students on the issues encountered in learning the English language skills using a blended learning modality. They have similar perspectives on the issues students experienced during the learning process.

Conclusion

Based on the foregoing findings, the researcher has come up with the following conclusions. The majority of the respondents were from IHA and VC, which were categorized as big schools compared to CMLI. Most of the respondents who participated in the survey were female. On the available devices at home, smartphones were commonly used as a device for learning in their respective homes. For the accessibility to connect to the internet, their own mobile data was widely used since most of the respondents used smartphones for blended learning. Grade 10 private junior high school students pointed out that reading skills is the most difficult to learn and is frequently encountered issues in learning English language skills using a blended learning modality. Profile of the students on the perceived issues in learning English language skills using blended learning modality had no significant difference. That students and teachers have similar viewpoints on the issues experienced in the teaching – learning process. Both students and teachers are still adapting to the new normal way of delivery of learning and embracing the emerging trends of technology. Significantly, students and teachers affirmed and had a similar viewpoint on the issues experienced in the teaching-learning process in the new normal. Consequently, the study shows that there was a significant relationship between their perceptions of the issues in learning the English subject using blended learning and the profile of the respondents, specifically on their school affiliation and the gadgets used during learning. It reveals that their profile influenced how they perceived issues that they have encountered since they are neophytes of the blended learning modality. Respondents are still adjusting to the implementation of blended learning modality.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

In light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the researcher hereby recommends the following:

SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION

Should conduct webinars and trainings for teachers to upgrade the teaching-learning process and improve efficiency in learning English language skills using blended learning modality during this pandemic. Provide one-on-one coaching for teachers in navigating the different online platforms to address the demands of the online world. On the other hand, assess teachers in crafting their learning packets to meet the needs of the students. Implement progress monitoring in cascading the knowledge acquired by teachers during the seminars and trainings attended. Keep track of learners' performance based on the strategies employed by the teachers using blended learning modality.

FUTURE RESEARCHERS

Conduct more studies about the issues encountered in learning English language skills using blended learning modality and ways to increase students' engagement for learning.

TEACHER

Utilize and adapt new strategies in teaching the English language using blended learning modality to facilitate active learning, which promotes deeper understanding and comprehension. Engage students to explore learning experiences through the use of different online platforms, films, television shows, popular music, news stories, literature, documentaries, and videos from sources such as YouTube. Employ new strategies and provide engaging activities and materials suited to the students' needs and the mode of learning. Make an action plan on Learning the English Language Skills using Blended Learning Modality.

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